

F. Schweiger: Suffixaufnahme and agreement in Australian languages

Abstract

Suffixaufnahme and multiple case marking in Australian languages have been discussed in several papers. In this paper possessive noun phrases and noun phrases with adjectives or demonstratives are compared. In most of the languages considered the same construction is used but there are some exceptions. This observation leads back to the question if genitive marked nouns are derived adjectives. Some Australian languages do not support a conjecture of Moravcsik.

0. Introduction

The adnominal function relates two nominals or noun phrases within a noun phrase. The genitive is the prototypical example which indicates such a relation. In many Australian languages there are other suffixes which can also indicate such a relation. One is the proprietive or comitative suffix which means “having”. A discussion of this suffix in about twenty languages can be found in the chapter *The derivational affix ‘having’* of Dixon 1976. We give two examples from DIYARI and from GUUGU YIMIDHIRR.

karna nganka-nhtha-li nganha rnanda-yi
 man beard-PROP-ERG 1sgO hit-PRES

The bearded man is hitting me. (Austin 1981:42)

nyulu gada-y bidha wangaarr-ga-mu-dhirr
 3sgSA come-PAST child white man-GEN-LIG-COM

He came with the white man’s child. (Haviland 1979:59)

Corresponding to this suffix is the privative suffix which means “lacking”. The next example is also from GUUGU YIMIDHIRR.

ngayu galga-mul
 1sgSA spear-PRIV

I am without a spear. (Haviland 1979:59)

The fact that both suffixes derive nominals which can bear case-marking raised many discussions about the status of these suffixes, including the genitive suffix. Blake proposed the term pre-case suffixes (Blake 1987:81), but this proposal was not followed up. However, Dench and Evans give

examples of Suffixaufnahme occurring with cases whose primary function is not adnominal (an in-depth information on Suffixaufnahme is given in Plank 1995). We give one example from PANYJIMA.

<i>ngunha</i>	<i>watharri-ku</i>	<i>nyurna-yu</i>	<i>warrapa-la-ku</i>
that	look for-PRES	snake-ACC	grass-LOC-ACC
<i>karta-larta</i>	<i>kurrjarta-ngarni</i>		
poke-FUT	spear-PROP		

He is looking for the snake in the grass to stab it with a spear. (Dench & Evans 1988:8).

A discussion whether adnominal suffixes are derivational or inflectional can be found in Dench and Evans 1988. The existence of the so-called modal case marking in some languages further complicates this question (see also Dench and Evans 1988 and Nordlinger 2014).

Suffixaufnahme and multiple case marking in Australian languages have been discussed in several publications, e. g. Dench & Evans 1988, Austin 1995, Dench 1995, Evans 1995, Schweiger 1995, Nordlinger 1998b, and Nordlinger 2014. In this paper we compare possessive noun phrases (which consist of possessors and possessed nouns) with noun phrases with adjectives or demonstratives.

Word marking (or *complete concord*) means that all elements of the noun phrase are marked for case. In languages with *final marking* the final word usually bears the case marker. In languages with *head marking* the case marker appears on the head. If the first word of the noun phrase is marked for case we speak of *initial marking*. *Free marking* means that at least one word of the noun phrase is case marked. In Dench & Evans 1988 some examples from NYIGINA are given but no example with a genitive marked noun. The typology presented here is slightly different from Dench & Evans 1988 and Blake 1987 by the consideration of initial marking.

We find that the type of marking occasionally allows some exceptions. In many languages possessive noun phrases and noun phrases with adjectives or demonstratives follow the same type but this is not true for all languages. Dixon's statement about noun phrases with adjectives applies to many Australian languages "... a noun is only occasionally accompanied by an adjective." (Dixon 1977:122). Furthermore one has to find noun phrases in an oblique case, since intransitive subject and object are expressed by the unmarked absolutive in almost all Australian languages. We remark that the status of adjectives in Australian languages is controversial (see e. g. Dench 1995). In the epilogue on Suffixaufnahme the following generalization (G 18) was stated: „If a language has Suffixaufnahme, then adjectives agree with their heads in the same

category“ (Moravcsik 1995:474). The Australian languages Anguthimri (Crowley 1981) and Uradhi (Crowley 1983) do not fully support the conjecture of Moravcsik.

We further note that inalienable possession usually is expressed by juxtaposition. We give three examples from ALYAWARRA, ANGUTHIMRI, and YANKUNTJATJARRA. We remark that an interesting type of possessive construction is discussed in Meakins and Nordlinger 2017.

aringk-ila iltja awiya utnhika
 dog-ERG hand boy bite+PAST

The dog bit the boy's hand (Yallop 1977:119).

lu ma-rra ?wa kwa-rra nyu-γu
 3sgA man-ERG dog foot-INST kick-PAST

The man kicked the dog with his foot (Crowley 1981:179).

wati-ngku mara-ngku papa pu-ngu
 man-ERG hand-ERG dog hit-PAST

The man hit the dog with his hand (Goddard 1983:103).

In the next section we discuss 16 languages in alphabetical order.

1. Types of marking in Australian languages

1.1. We first look at ANGUTHIMRI.

lu wathayi-yamra-ma pat'a-ma pae-ni
 3sgS old man-GEN-ABL canoe-ABL come out-PAST

He got out of the old man's canoe. (Crowley 1981: 182)

This sentence shows word marking but Crowley remarks that the following adjective or demonstrative does not inflect for case (Crowley 1981:178). We give one example.

aju d'u'a ma-ŋa gera ŋa-thimri
 1sgS this man-LOC sit-PRES beard-PROP

I am sitting down with the man with a beard (Crowley 1981:168).

1.2. In BUNUBA the first word of the noun phrase is usually case marked. We remark that BUNUBA has only ten verb roots (e.g. RA, MA₂, WU, WU₂ in the following examples).

yarrangi-yawu *muway* *maaningarri* *ward-jiyirra*
1unrOBL-ALL country tomorrow go-1re+RA

Tomorrow we go to our country. (Rumsey 2000:115)

nhu-yani-ingga *garrawu* *wardba-wurrma*
3sgOBL-pl-ERG relations take-3sgO3nsgA+MA₂

His relations take him (Rumsey 2000:116).

wiyi-ngarri-u-ingga *jamayina* *duwa-wunu*
woman-COM₁-DAT-INST axe hit-3sgO3sgA+WU₂+PAST

He hit it with the axe belonging to a man with a wife. (Rumsey 2000:117)

niy-ingga *jajalingga* *nyarnungga-waniy-nhi*
that one-ERG parrot dive in-3sg+WU+PAST-3sgOBL

The parrot dived for it (Rumsey 2000:129).

wariyga-waniy *ngaala-yawu* *muway*
shift-3sg+WU+PAST different-ALL camp

He shifted to a different camp (Rumsey 2000:115).

1.3. Further examples come from DIYARI. The usual construction is final marking.

nhawu-ya *ngama-yi* *ngurra* *ngakarna-nhi*
3sg-near sit-PRES camp 1sg:DAT-LOC

He is sitting in my camp (Austin 1981:62).

karna *nganka-nhtha-li* *nganha* *rnanda-yi*
man beard-PROP-ERG 1sgO hit-PRES

The bearded man is hitting me (Austin 1981:42).

kupa *parrtyarna-li* *nganha* *nhayi-ya*

child all-ERG 1sgO see-PAST

All the children saw me (Austin 1981:58).

thana ngama-rna wapa-yi mitha muya-nhi

3plS sit-PART AUX-PRES country dry-LOC

They live in a dry country (Austin 1981:90).

But we have word marking if the noun phrase is split up or special emphasis is given.

kinhthala-li nhungkarni-yali nganha matha-rna warra-yi

dog-ERG 3sgnfDAT-ERG 1sgO bite-PART AUX-PRES

His dog (!) bit me (Austin 1981:94).

mankada-li nganha nhayi-rna warra-yi parlpa-yi

girl-ERG 1sgO see-PART AUX-PRES some-ERG

Some girls saw me (Austin 1981:94).

kupa-nhi nganhi yatha-na warra-yi kathi pani-nhi

child-LOC 1sgS speak-PART AUX-PRES clothes none-LOC

I spoke to the child with no clothes on (Austin 1981:44).

1.5. In the word marking language DJABUGAY the genitive marker is connected to the outer case marker by a ligative (or linking suffix).

ngawu bibuy-ngun-mu-nda gurra:-nda wa:-ng ma:

1SgA child-GEN-LIG-DAT dog-DAT give-PRES food

I give the child's dog (some) food (Patz 1991:269).

ngawu mulu-:rr gali-ng wabarr yalma-:rr

1sgA two-COM go-PRES hunt cross boomerang-COM

I go hunting with two cross boomerangs (Patz 1991:292).

1.6. The next language is the word marking language GUMBAYNGGIR.

yarrang *ni:garr* *gudyu:* *niyanggidam* *gayi* *nganyundi-ya*
 DEM man LOCDEIC 3plS talk+PRES 1sgGEN-LOC
gagu:-ngumbala
 brother-LOC

Those men over there are talking to my brother. (Eades 1979:317)

ba:ba-gu *dyunuy-gundi-yu* *dyu:n.gu* *dyala:ny* *dyamay* *barrway.*
 father-ERG small-GEN-ERG say+FUT tongue too big

The child's father will say '(your) mouth is too big'. (Eades 1979:277)

barrway-dyu *ni:ga-du* *buwa:ng* *gi:barr* *dyunuy*
 big-ERG man-ERG hit+PAST child small

The big man hit the small child (Eades 1979:272)

However, word marking is not obligatory.

ma:na *nga:lu* *ni:garr-gundi* *nyami:-gu*
 take+IMP water man-GEN woman-ALL

Take water to the man's wife. (Eades 1979:317)

An example of reduced genitive marking is the following sentence.

warru *nginundi* *buwa:rr* *bidya:rr*
 who 2sgGEN baby name

What is your baby's name? (Eades 1979:317)

1.7. GUUGU YIMIDHIRR is also a final marking language.

biiba *yarrga-aga-mu-n* *gudaa* *gunda-y*
 father boy-GEN-LIG-ERG dog hit-PAST

The boy's father hit the dog (Haviland 1979: 57).

However, if the constituent is split up word marking occurs.

yarrga-aga-mu-n *gudaa* *gunda-y* *biiba-ngun*
 boy-GEN-LIG-ERG dog hit-PAST father-ERG

The boy's father hit the dog (Haviland 1979: 57).

nambal warrga-al dyaarba baydya-rrin nyulu
 rock big-INST snake cover-PAST 3sg

He crushed the snake with a large stone (Haviland 1979:103).

1.8. The word marking language KALKATUNGU also uses a ligative.

kalpin-ku-wa-thu yaun-ku-wa-thu thuku-yu ityayi-ngi
 man-GEN-LIG-ERG big-GEN-LIG-ERG dog-ERG bite-1sgO

The big man's dog bit me (Blake 1987:87).

In KALKATUNGU there are some instances of the ligative *-wa* being used when no further suffix follows. Note that the absolutive of nouns has no overt case marker.

marapai-thu ngatyi-wa thuku lhayi-nha
 woman-ERG 1sgDAT-LIG dog hit-PAST

The woman hit my dog (Blake 1979:50).

tyipa-yi thuku-yu yaun-tu yanyi itya-mi
 this-ERG dog-ERG big-ERG white man bite-FUT

This big dog will bite the white man (Blake 1987:87).

1.9. MANGARAYI has head marking for possessive phrases but word marking for noun phrases with adjectives or demonstratives. *-3* is a verbal prefix used under specific conditions (See Merlan 1982:143-144).

rna-bugbung-gu ϕ -barnam-rnawung-garlama ga-nga-yag
 mGEN-old man-DAT nALL-camp-3sgPOSS-ALL -3-1sg-go

I'm going to the old man's camp (Merlan 1982:66).

ϕ -balayi-wana ϕ -rlandi-wana
 nABL-big-ABL nABL-tree-ABL

'from the big tree' (Merlan 1982:51)

1.10. NGAANYATJARRA is final marking.

pitja-ngu munga-ngka purni-lu muni tju-nu rabbit-ku trap-ngka

come-PASTP night-LOC horse-ERG lip put-PASTP rabbit-GEN trap-LOC

A horse came last night and put its lip in the rabbit trap (Glass 1983:21).

papa maru-lu-rni patja-rnu
 dog black-ERG-1sgO bite-PASTP

The black dog bit me (Glass 1983:46).

1.11. A typical example for a word marking language is NGIYAMBAA.

ɲadhu giyanhdha-nha ɲidji-la: winarr-gu-dhi mirri-dji
 1SgS be afraid-PRES this+CIRC-EST woman-DAT-CIRC dog-CIRC

I am frightened of this woman's dog (Donaldson 1980:107).

bungu-bu-lu-niŋgal miyi babirr-u dhiŋga:ŋ-gu
 many-UNIV-3sgA-3plO makePAST big-ERG creature-ERG

He made them all, the huge creature (Donaldson 1980:316).

1.12. An interesting language is NUNGGUBUYU. Heath states that noun phrases with adjectives can be word-marked or the marking is on the head noun but most examples are not case-marked by an overt suffix. Agreement can also be seen by the optional class marking prefix.

a-wurugu-wuy a-runggal-wuy
 CM-pond.ALL CM-big-ALL

'to the big pond' (Heath 1984:152)

wu-wayama-ni wu-dhanguny runggal
 3sgCM-proceed-NONPAST₂ CM-wind big

'the big wind runs ...' (Heath 1980:285)

ana-wardawardard ana-lha:wu
 CM-strong CM-word

'strong (=secret) words' (Heath 1980:250)

Noun phrases with a pronominal possessor can have word marking or free marking. If the relative marker which also has the function of a genitive is used the head is marked. If the relative marker REL is not used the pronoun usually has the oblique form.

nurri-nyinyung *ana-lha:l-waj*
 1expl-REL CM-country-PERG
 ‘in/around our country’ (Heath 1984:546)

nigawi-ruj *a:-'nga-ruj*
 3sgOBL-LOC CM- camp-LOC
 ‘at his camp’ (Heath 1984:546)

ngayawi-wuy *a-lh:al*
 1sgOBL-ALL CM-country
 ‘to my country’ (Heath 1984:547)

1.13. According to Dench & Evans 1988 NYIGINA has free marking. Some examples are given but no example with a genitive marked noun is given. Two sentences from Nyigina illustrate this. Popular locations of the noun phrase suffix are the initial item or the most significant item.

gudyarra-ni *wamba* *mug* *yirrinymirri* *yila*
 two-ERG man hit 3duA3sgOmake dog

Two men hit the dog (Dench&Evans 1988: 5).

yindyina *ginya marnin-ga* *wurrawurra-ni*
 3sgA3sgIOSay DEM woman-EMPH specific name-ERG

That wurrawurra woman says to him (Dench&Evans 1988: 6).

1. 14 We next consider URADHI. Crowley states “Adjectives can potentially take the same case suffixes as nouns, though they rarely do, unless the head noun is absent.” (Crowley 1989:334). In the data I could only find one example of a case-marked noun phrase with an adjective.

utaya-mpu *amanyama-(mpu)* *uḡumpuny* *iyanhanga-n*
 dog-ERG big-(ERG) back break-PAST
 The big dog broke [the other dog's] back. (Crowley 1983:372)

But suffixaufnahme normally is connected with word marking.

ulu *awutyi-ngu* *wutpu-:namu-ngu* *intya*
 3sgS house-OBL old man-GEN-OBL live.PRES
 He lives in the old man's house. (Crowley 1983:377)

wutpu-:namu-mun *γantu-mun* *anhthaβa-ny*
 old man-GEN-ABL canoe-ABL take-PAST
 [They] took [it] out of the old man's canoe. (Crowley 1983:377)

ama-:lu *ngampu-kyama-ngku* *minha* *ungye-al*
 man-ERG tooth-PRIV-ERG meat eat-PRES
 The toothless man is eating the meat. (Crowley 1983:349)

1.15. WAMBAYA usually has head marking in possessive noun phrases. It has two suffixes which signal possession, a dative suffix and a genitive suffix. The latter suffix is congruent with the noun class of the possessor.

mirra *ngi* *jalyu-ni* *bungmanyi-nka*
 sit 1sgS bed.IV-LOC old man.I-DAT
 I'm sitting on the old man's bed (Nordlinger 1998a:90).

yarru *ngi* *bungmanya-naganka* *magi-nmanji*
 go 1sgS old woman.II-GEN.IV camp.IV-ALL
 I'm going to the old woman's camp (Nordlinger 1998a:93).

Nordlinger reports that she once used the construction

mirra *ngi* *alangi-niganka-ni* *jalyu-ni*
 sit 1sg boy-GEN.IV-LOC bed.IV-LOC

I'm sitting on the boy's bed (Nordlinger 1998a:93).

About this construction Nordlinger writes: "Speakers will accept as grammatical examples ... although they do not produce such examples themselves."

However, kinship possessor phrases have full concord.

<i>gujiga-ny-i-ni</i>	<i>janyi-ni</i>	<i>gini-ng-a</i>	<i>dawu</i>
mother.II-GEN.I-ERG	dog.I-ERG	3sgm-1O-PAST	bite.

Mother's dog bit me (Nordlinger 1998a:94).

Other noun phrases show full concord.

<i>manngurru</i>	<i>ngi-nng-a</i>	<i>maliwa-nka</i>	<i>jarrawaja-nka</i>
be ashamed	1sg-RR-NFUT	big.IV-DAT	trousers.IV-DAT

I'm embarrassed about his big trousers (Nordlinger 1998a:89).

1.16. In the head marking language WARDAMAN a dative marked nominal or pronominal possessor cannot be further inflected.

<i>nganinggin-gu</i>	<i>yi-guyu-wu</i>	<i>minini-yi</i>	<i>nga(n)-la-rri</i>
1sgGEN-DAT	CM-mother-DAT	dog-ERG	3sgA1sgO-bite-PAST

My mother's dog bit me (Merlan 1994:74).

But with adjectives or demonstrative pronouns we find word marking.

<i>ya-wurr-ga-n</i>	<i>yirrgulu-warr</i>	<i>wu-jad-garr</i>
3-3nsg-take-PRES	river-ALL	CM-big-ALL

They're taking it to the big river (Merlan 1994:77).

The use of the prefix *-ya* (labelled by 3) is explained in Merlan 1994:124.

<i>dang-ni</i>	<i>wunggun-bu-ndi</i>	<i>yibiyani-yi</i>
that-ERG	3sgA3nsgO-hit-PAST	man-ERG

That man hit them (Merlan 1994:64).

1.16. The last language is YIDINY which has word marking.

<i>milba:n</i>	<i>wagudya-ni</i>	<i>yiŋu</i>	<i>guda:ga</i>
clever+GEN	man-GEN	this	dog

This dog (belongs) to the clever man (Dixon 1977:149).

gudaga-ŋgu wagal-ni- ŋgu ŋanyany badya:l
 dog-ERG wife-GEN-ERG 1sgO bite+PAST
 (My) wife's dog bit me (Dixon 1977:134).

nyundu minya ŋuŋu wiwin gudaga-nda bimbi-nu-nda.
 2sgA meat that give+IMP dog-DAT father-GEN-DAT
 You give that meat to father's dog (Dixon 1977:136).

2. Conclusion

The idea that genitive marked nouns are derivations, i. e. they behave like adjectives, has already been discussed for Australian languages (see e. g. Dench & Evans 1988). In this paper we give some examples that possessive noun phrases and noun phrases with adjectives can be constructed in different ways.

Our results may be summarized in the following table. Languages with different types of marking are given in bold face.

	Possessive noun phrases	Noun phrases with Adjectives or demonstratives
Anguthimri	word marking	head marking
Bunuba	initial marking	initial marking
Diyari	final marking	final marking
Djabugay	word marking	word marking
Gumbaynggir	word marking	word marking
Guugu Yimidhirr	final marking	final marking
Kalkatungu	word marking	word marking
Mangarayi	head marking	word marking
Ngaanyatjarra	final marking	final marking
Ngiyambaa	word marking	word marking
Nunggubuyu	various patterns	various patterns
Nyigina	no data found	free marking
Uradhi	word marking	head marking

Wambaya	head marking	word marking
Wardaman	head marking	word marking
Yidiny	word marking	word marking

List of abbreviations:

A agent, ABL ablative, ALL allative, AUX auxiliar verb, CM class marker, CIRC circumstantive, COM comitative, DAT dative, DEIC deictic, DEM demonstrative, du dual, EMPH emphatic clitic, ERG ergative, EST established reference, ex exclusive, GEN genitive, f feminine, FUT future, IMP imperative, INST instrumental, IO indirect object, LIG ligative, LOC locative, m masculine, n neutrum, nf non-feminine, nm non-masculine, NFUT non-future, NPAST non-past, nsg non-singular, O object, OBL oblique, PART participle, PAST past, PASTP past perfective, PERG pergressive, pl plural, POSS possessive, PRES present, PRIV privative, PROP proprietive, re restricted, REL relative, RR reflexive/reciprocal, sg singular, S intransitive subject, UNIV universal quantifier, unr unrestricted, 1,2,3 1st, 2nd, 3rd person

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